

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B093
Date: 11 May 2005
Take Off 09:59:17
Landing: 14:41:37
Flight Time 4h42m20

Campaign: Test Flight
Trials Instructions: Rosemount Probes
Operating Area: North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	Co-pilot training	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight
4	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
5	Aircraft Scientist	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
7	Mission Scientist Training	Jonathan Smith	Leeds University
8	Flight Manager Training	Jim Crawford	FAAM
9	CCM2 Training + CCN	Paul James	FAAM
10	CCN Training	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
11	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
12	Cloud Physics	Martin Pickering	Met Office
13	CCM2	Sue Angold	Directflight
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B093 Track 11-MAY-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B093

Date:

Project:

Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
094231		Engine Start	-.03 kft	126	
094843		Taxy Start	-.03 kft	128	
095917		T/O	-.03 kft	031	from cranfield
100331		asp open	5.1 kft	350	
102828	104421	Profile 1	11.0 - -.34 kft	015	
103440		Profile 1	4.8 kft	014	change rate of descen
104456	104705	Run 1.1	-.25 - -.26 kft	351	vmin heaters on
104740	104941	Run 1.2	-.28 - -.29 kft	357	vmax
104941	105212	Run 1.3	-.29 - -.28 kft	001	vmax heaters off
105307	105507	Run 1.4	-.25 - -.26 kft	357	vmin
105516	105706	Profile 2	-.23 - 0.72 kft	358	
105707	110045	Run 2.1	0.72 - 0.71 kft	001	
105820		Run 2.1	0.72 kft	011	vmin htrs on
110045	110244	Run 3.1	0.71 - 1.4 kft	016	pitch
110341	110547	Run 3.2	0.70 - 0.69 kft	019	straight
110738	110940	Run 3.3	0.70 - 0.69 kft	177	yaw
111001	111158	Run 4	0.68 - 0.69 kft	176	heaters off
111210	111406	Run 5.1	0.80 - 1.3 kft	174	pitch
111442	111650	Run 5.2	0.67 - 0.72 kft	193	straight
111651	111847	Run 5.3	0.72 - 0.75 kft	221	yaw
111950	112449	Profile 3	0.73 - 5.0 kft	289	
112513	112653	Run 6.1	5.0 kft	239	vmin
112738	112940	Run 6.2	5.0 kft	238	vmax
113125	113552	Profile 4	5.1 - 10.0 kft	044	science spd
113610	113712	Run 7.1	10.0 kft	045	sci spd
113754	113958	Run 7.2	10.0 kft	043	vmin
114145	114344	Run 7.3	10.0 kft	046	vmax
114345	114404	Run 7.4	10.0 kft	044	heaters on
114516	114612	Run 7.5	9.9 - 10.0 kft	007	sci speed
114640	114839	Run 7.6	10.0 kft	044	vmin
115019	115220	Run 7.7	10.0 kft	176	vmax
115220	120751	Profile 5	10.0 - 25.0 kft	178	
120855	121057	Run 8.1	25.0 kft	291	sci spd heaters off
121138	121337	Run 8.2	25.0 kft	300	vmin
121610	121811	Run 8.3	25.0 kft	297	vmax
122002	122216	Run 8.4	25.0 - 26.7 kft	085	pitch
122401	122608	Run 8.5	25.0 kft	091	straight
122617	122820	Run 8.6	25.0 kft	088	yaw
122854	123111	Orbit 1	25.1 kft	086	right hand
123128	123257	Orbit 2	25.1 - 24.9 kft	115	heaters on
123338	123510	Orbit 3	25.1 - 25.0 kft	075	
123535	123635	Run 8.7	25.1 - 25.0 kft	094	straight and level
123838	124320	Profile 6	25.1 - 30.0 kft	262	
124355	124556	Run 9.1	30.0 kft	275	sci spd heaters off
124633	124837	Run 9.2	30.0 kft	277	vmin
125041	125242	Run 9.3	30.0 kft	273	vmax
125539	130009	Profile 7	30.0 - 33.0 kft	092	
130018	130125	Run 10.1	33.1 - 33.0 kft	088	sci spd heaters on
130504	130705	Run 10.2	33.0 kft	275	vmax
130820	131024	Run 10.3	33.0 kft	270	vmin
131217	131417	Run 10.4	33.0 kft	266	sci spd, htrs off
131738	131939	Run 10.5	33.0 kft	090	vmax
132027	132227	Run 10.6	32.9 - 33.0 kft	086	vmin
132248	133337	Profile 8	33.1 - 25.0 kft	088	
132657		Profile 8	29.0 kft	086	interrupt
132914		Profile 8	29.1 kft	275	resume
133344	133538	Run 11.1	25.0 kft	268	straight heaters on
133612	133820	Run 11.2	25.0 - 25.1 kft	269	pitch
133838	134041	Run 11.3	25.1 kft	268	straight
134059	134302	Run 11.4	25.0 kft	268	straight

134512	134730	Run 11.5	25.0 kft	087 yaw
134808	140658	Profile 9	25.0 - 10.0 kft	089 intrpted + resumed
140658	140902	Run 12.1	10.0 kft	227 sci spd
140936	141139	Run 12.2	10.0 kft	227 vmin
141307	141508	Run 12.3	10.0 kft	226 vmax
141630	141832	Run 12.4	10.0 kft	225 sci spd + heaters off
141901	142103	Run 12.5	10.0 kft	224 vmin
142232	142434	Run 12.6	10.1 - 10.0 kft	224 vmax
143010		asp closed	5.8 kft	237
144137		Land	0.00 kft	034 at cranfield
144609		standstill	0.00 kft	305 52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B093 Track 11-MAY-05

Rosemount Temperature Sensor Characterisation Sortie

JAS
Jonathan Smith
U. Leeds

Contact: Jonathan P Taylor

10:15
clear
aircraft

Scientific aims: The Rosemount Temperature Sensors have been changed and there is uncertainty about their response to changes in pitch and yaw. Also the recovery factors need to be computed for the new configuration.

Weather requirements: Clear sky column, i.e. absence of clouds at all levels.

Special Instrument Requirements: De-iced Rosemount Sensor to have heaters on and off according to instructions given for each leg of flight.

V_{max} 250 low
 V_{min} 195

Operating area – to be chosen in cloud free conditions over ocean.

1. Take off and transit to operating area at altitude chosen at discretion of air crew noting that science will start with low level runs (45mins) – heaters on
2. Profile descent from transit altitude to 50ft at 1000ft/min reducing to 500ft/min in boundary layer (20mins) – heaters on
3. Perform straight and level run at 100ft, accelerate to V_{max} and then fly straight and level for 2mins, then decelerate to V_{min} and then fly 2mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
4. Repeat item 3 (10 mins) – heaters ON
5. Profile ascent to 1000ft at 500ft/min (2 mins) – heaters on
6. Fly straight and level for 2 mins, then induce pitch oscillations (+/-10 degrees) for 2 mins, followed by straight and level for 2 mins (6 mins) – heaters on
7. Fly straight and level for 2 mins, then induce yaw oscillations (+/-10 degrees) for 2 mins, followed by straight and level for 2 mins (6 mins) – heaters on
8. Repeat items 6 and 7 (12 mins) – heaters OFF
9. Profile ascent to FL050 at 1000ft/min (4 mins) – heaters off
10. Perform straight and level run at 5000ft, accelerate to V_{max} and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to V_{min} and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
11. Profile ascent to FL100 at 1000ft/min (5mins) – heaters off
12. Perform straight and level run at FL100 accelerate to V_{max} and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to V_{min} and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
13. Repeat item 12 (10mins) – heaters ON
14. Profile ascent to FL250 at 1000ft/min (15mins) – heaters off
15. Perform straight and level run at FL250 accelerate to V_{max} and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to V_{min} and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
16. Fly straight and level for 2 mins, then induce pitch oscillations (+/-10 degrees) for 2 mins, followed by straight and level for 2 mins (6 mins) – heaters on
17. Fly straight and level for 2 mins, then induce yaw oscillations (+/-10 degrees) for 2 mins, followed by straight and level for 2 mins (6 mins) – heaters on
18. Fly an orbit (360° banked turn) in a clockwise direction (5 mins)
19. Fly an orbit (360° banked turn) in an anti-clockwise direction (5 mins)
20. Profile ascent to FL300 at 1000ft/min (5 mins) – heaters on
21. Perform straight and level run at FL300 accelerate to V_{max} and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to V_{min} and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
22. Profile ascent to FL350 (10mins) – heaters ON
23. Perform straight and level run at FL350 accelerate to V_{max} and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to V_{min} and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins). – heaters on
24. Repeat item 21 (10mins) – heaters OFF.
25. Transit to Cranfield (45 mins) – heaters off

300 FL100

11:25
sun to port now
P down to
these
2nd time
ward

20 - data book etc so far

Total sortie time: 300 mins

h/v2

Rosemount Temperature Sensor Characterisation Sortie

Contact: Jonathan P Taylor

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 2. Profile descent from transit altitude to 50ft at 1000ft/min reducing to 500ft/min in boundary layer (20mins) – heaters on
 3. Perform straight and level run at 100ft, accelerate to Vmax and then fly straight and level for 2mins, then decelerate to Vmin and then fly 2mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
 4. Repeat item 3 (10 mins) – heaters ON
 5. Profile ascent to 1000ft at 500ft/min (2 mins) – heaters on
 6. Fly straight and level for 2 mins, then induce pitch oscillations (+/-10 degrees) for 2 mins, followed by straight and level for 2 mins (6 mins) – heaters on
 7. Fly straight and level for 2 mins, then induce yaw oscillations (+/-10 degrees) for 2 mins, followed by straight and level for 2 mins (6 mins) – heaters on
 8. Repeat items 6 and 7 (12 mins) – heaters OFF
 9. Profile ascent to FL050 at 1000ft/min (4 mins) – heaters off
 10. Perform straight and level run at 5000ft, accelerate to Vmax and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to Vmin and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
 11. Profile ascent to FL100 at 1000ft/min (5mins) – heaters off
 12. Perform straight and level run at FL100 accelerate to Vmax and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to Vmin and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
 13. Repeat item 12 (10mins) – heaters ON
 14. Profile ascent to FL250 at 1000ft/min (15mins) – heaters off
 15. Perform straight and level run at FL250 accelerate to Vmax and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to Vmin and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
 16. Fly straight and level for 2 mins, then induce pitch oscillations (+/-10 degrees) for 2 mins, followed by straight and level for 2 mins (6 mins) – heaters on
 17. Fly straight and level for 2 mins, then induce yaw oscillations (+/-10 degrees) for 2 mins, followed by straight and level for 2 mins (6 mins) – heaters on
 18. Fly an orbit (360° banked turn) in a clockwise direction (5 mins)
 19. Fly an orbit (360° banked turn) in an anti-clockwise direction (5 mins)
 20. Profile ascent to FL300 at 1000ft/min (5 mins) – heaters on
 21. Perform straight and level run at FL300 accelerate to Vmax and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to Vmin and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins) – heaters off
 22. Profile ascent to FL350 (10mins) – heaters ON
 23. Perform straight and level run at FL350 accelerate to Vmax and then fly straight and level for 2 mins, then decelerate to Vmin and then fly 2 mins straight and level (10mins). – heaters on
 24. Repeat item 21 (10mins) – heaters OFF.
 25. Transit to Cranfield (45 mins) – heaters off
- Total sortie time: 300 mins

Mission Scientist's Debrief

Flight No : B093

Date : 11/05/05

Assessment of the flight

This was a successful sortie to characterise the Rosemount temperature sensors. There was concern initially that we would not be able cover all of the items on the sortie brief because the Vmax runs would chew through the fuel and reduce our flight time. So initially the Vscience speed runs were trimmed out. When it became evident that this wasn't a problem and also, that the temperatures were drifting during the first run after changing level, we then included a 2-minute Vscience run at the start of subsequent runs.

After take-off we transited to the N Sea at FL110 over a bank of SCu. The profile from take-off is shown in *B093_profile_t_o1017Z.PDF*. The cloud broke up readily about 15 miles east of the E Anglia coast.

We profiled down into the operating area with the heaters on, noting the top of the inversion at FL39. The inversion over the sea was less distinct than over the land, see *B093_2profile1046Z.PDF* with both profiles overlaid. A slow turn was performed to avoid cloud at FL24. We then started with the low level runs at 100ft. It was clear at this height although we did fly underneath some small Cu (base ~1500ft, visible in UFC @ 10:42:21). More structure was noticed on the DI signal with the heater switched on compared to off. Vmax 250kts and Vmin 195kts.

The 1000ft runs were carried out with pitch variations from +16° to 0° then a S&L run and the roll varying from +7° to -6° during the yaw variations. The sun was shining on the temp sensors for the first set of these runs (R3.1,2,3). *B093_swapover1120Z.PDF* shows the change in offset when the heater is switched. Compared with yaw, the pitch changes cause a greater change in temperature, the least change turbulence probe signal.

As we profiled up to FL50 we went through the inversion at FL25. The 2 temperature signals were within ~0.3° at Vmin compared to ~0.1 at Vmax. Also, it was noticed that during the Vmin run, the temperatures were drifting downwards. The drift in both temperatures after reaching FL50 is shown in *B093_settle_drift1135Z.PDF*.

At FL100 it became increasingly moist after 1150Z and remained so for the rest of the sortie. We got out of sequence with the heater settings on the FL250 runs. This wasn't spotted until we starting the first orbit. It was duly aborted until we sorted things out, then continued with first a clockwise orbit, O2 with 45° bank followed by an anticlockwise orbit, O3.

At FL300 the gap between Vmin and Vmax started dropping off. Vmin was 190kts and Vmax, 230kts. As this would get worse the higher we climbed, we decided to carry out the max altitude runs at FL330 even though we could have climbed higher by that stage.

On descent approach, passed through cloud, though volume of other air traffic prevented this being extended to provide more data for cloud physics probes.

Summary of the weather conditions

An anticyclone centred off the SW of S. Ireland was feeding a thin veil of cirrus over Ireland and Scotland. This was dissipating as it got to about 55N over the N. Sea. There was about 1/8th cumulus initially which increased slightly during the early part of the sortie then began to dissipate during the afternoon. At 1405Z there was 3/8th As or Cs above, and hazy down to a calm sea. It was relatively moist between FL150 and FL330. There was much more Cu over the land. On crossing the coast during transit return, cloud increased to 6/8th Cu below, 4/8th Cs aloft.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.093**.....

 Date **11.5.05**.....

 Page **1**... of **2**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
101221	transit	FL110	058	52.4N 0.0E	5/8 Scu tops @ Skft, 1/8 Ci, hazy.
102827	P1	FL110	015	52.9N 1.4E	Scu sheet ends ≈ 15m NE of coast, clear below 1/8 Cu
103631	P1	FL39	014	53.3N 1.6E	Top of B. Layer (was F150 on initial climb)
103839	P1	FL24			Slow turn to avoid cloud ahead base 1450 ft.
104456	R1	100'	351	53.8N 1.8E	Clr at 100ft 1/8 Cu, 1/8 Ci, less hazy, lots of birds
		100'			Vmax 250kts, Vmin 195kts
110250	R3	1000'	020°	^	+16° max, 0° min pitch, ^{sun on sensors} +7°, -6° roll
111213	R5.1	1000'	174°		+15°, 0° pitch, +5, -5 roll.
112220	P3	FL25	238°		Inversion lvl.
113537	P3	FL100	045	54.2N 1.1E	2/8 Cu/Scu, 1/8 Ci
115250	P8	FL100	178		Becoming more moist at this level.
115846	P6	FL159	178	54.0N 2.4E	Moist to this level then drying out slightly
120331	P6	FL207	219	53.6N 2.4E	2/8 Cirrus
					Will do 2min science run before Vmax/min to allow probes to settle. No drift this time
121647	R8.3	FL250			Vmax = 250kts Vmin =
122002	R8.4	"	093	53.7N 1.0E	Pitch = Pitch +15, -10
					2/8 Cu 1/8 Cu, clear above, hazy ahead
122725	R8.7	FL250	088	53.7N 2.1E	Roll -13° to +10°
123128	02	FL250	130°		Orbit, 45° bank ^{about 90} clockwise
123338	03		040°		Orbit 45° bank a.c.w.
123535	R9.1 R8.8	FL250	092°	53.6N 2.6E	S + L Run science
					Vmin 190kIAS, Vmax. 230kIAS.
125759	P9	FL319	088		2/8 Cu 1/8 Scu, 1/8 Ci, clear above.
1300		FL330			Science run @ max alt.

Training Mission Scientist log (training) Jonathan Smith B093

t/o en at ~ 6/8 above

close 920 hPa break 898
water cell @ 861 hPa at 10:02:16
~ 849 hPa

JAS
page 1 of 2

8h2 to p again 10:02:55 ish -4°C

water limit 10:03:29

strong inversion 816 hPa at ~ -1.5°C

< in reaching inversion, odd time getting above but layer

892 hPa 10:36 is base of inversion ~~is~~ out over sea
mistless cloud.

10:40 nice clouds ahead

10:41:50 pass under the clouds, maybe not directly under (some
UFC)
10:42:21

birds on sea 10:44:53

R1 100 ft. under some cloud.

10:54:50 - more structure on heater on section R1.3 → 1.4

R3.2 at end 11:06 max cloud above

B3.3 11:07:38 you now

11:12: some cloud

11:18 heaters off deiced is warmer - will avoid cloud on climb
turnaround at some stage may coincide with heater on/off
differences

note at V_{min} V_{max} at 5000 ft the temp. kept drifting down
during V_{min} - still settling to new altitude

11:48 @ 696 hPa difference between ~~prob~~ ND D is greater now at
this altitude
+ we turn reciprocal.
sun ahead

11:46 rms 1135 v_{min} No greater 11:40 snap over an increase in speed

Training

Mission Scientist's Log

JAS
P1 on back of brief
↑
Page 2 of 2

Flight No **B.093**.....

Date 11 May 05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:17	R8.3	FL250	297	53°5'N 1°5'E	temp snap over again with high speed sun was behind ← the best position?
12:20	R8.4	"	90		pitch down + descend Non on top / " up + ascend " " "
12:24					
12:28					temp diff snaps over start yaw non de on top wd yaw non de on top
12:33					orbit deiced heats up
12:30					earlier heater on plots ~ 0.5 deg on deiced
12:40					3/W drops down at Vmax
12:45	R9.1	FL300	275		small cu below, no ice though
12:48	R9.2				temp diff up on ↑ + start of this at Vmin on profile before Deiced on top, on sci speed together, at Vmin Non on top
12:57					Ci to part, maybe more above
13:13					lots of cu over land, follows coastline with less over sea, no sign of ice
13:21					break out as sci speed ok
13:36					nice jump in deiced temp at start of pitch up.
14:03	in P10				now up front 2/8 cu below 3/8 As/cs above, hazy, sea state, calm (white)
14:13:22					T's come close but then separate again @ Vmax 347 kn
14:15					heater off - spot on plot

14:17

crossing coast now 6/8 Cu below 4/8 ~~CS~~ Cs above

cloud

14:19:30 to Vmin

debit
16.15
local

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Y
All cylinders pressures are OK	Y
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	Y

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT			
POST FLIGHT	25	131	139

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)							
NO (ppbV)							
NO₂ (ppbV)							
NO_x (ppbV)							
SO₂ (ppbV)							

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL		Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
09:43:03	Ground (during engine start)	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		92.34	81.87	7559.50	44.79	7.16	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		34.62	16	17			
10:19:07	FL110 (596-496)	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		89.17	81.49	7310.69	47.24	7.15	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		34.00	61	62	1.074	0.067	0.346
10:38:38	FL021	Remarks					
		Nox lamp alarm as Lamp voltage 0.1V high (51.1V)					
10:47:56	100'	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		88.52	82.66	7316.71	43.62 (loose card?)	6.42	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		30.42	23	24	1.124	0.068	0.493
11:00:45	700'	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		88.57	82.63	7318.01	48.21	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.98	29	30	1.114	0.064	0.466
11:14	700'	Remarks					
		Zero / cal valve check = 513 = OK, no need for full cal.					
11:28:03	FL050	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		87.91	82.00	7279.09	48.88	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.98	50	49	1.104	0.070	0.419
11:49:50	FL100	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		87.82	81.62	7167.16	49.19	7.16	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		34.94	62	62	1.069	0.065	0.339

Time	Flight Level	Remarks				
	FL250	Two bad calcs due to Cal gas valve having been closed during instrument warm-up. Gas turned on again and next cal completed successfully.				
Time	Flight Level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
12:20:30	FL250	19.48	358.34	6981.07	49.75	7.14
		Flows (LPM unless stated)				
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator
		33.93	-	-	-	-
Time	Flight Level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
12:47:24	FL300	85.83	81.18	6967.30	49.57	6.79
		Flows (LPM unless stated)				
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator
		33.91	-	-	0.971	0.065
Time	Flight Level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
13:05:39	FL330	83.60	83.55	6989.55	49.56	6.46
		Flows (LPM unless stated)				
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator
		33.91	-	-	0.938	0.065
Time	Flight Level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
13:40:05	FL250	87.54	79.74	6980.33	48.41	7.13
		Flows (LPM unless stated)				
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator
		33.95	-	-	0.990	0.067
Time	Flight Level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
14:10:09	FL100	89.40	80.52	7198.04	47.64	7.14
		Flows (LPM unless stated)				
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator
		33.95	-	-	-	-
Time	Flight Level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
		Flows (LPM unless stated)				
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator
Time	Flight Level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
		Flows (LPM unless stated)				
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator

FLIGHT NUMBER: B093	DATE: 11 May 2005	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	Page 4 of 4
PROJECT: Rosemount Calibration Flight			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

CO instrument Cal gas had been closed during instrument warm-up to conserve gas. Pressure in pipes remained for initial calibrations but dropped out after a couple of hours. Once spotted opening the cylinder solved the problem.

Nox chamber alarm keeps coming on for a few seconds but only 0.1 degree too high!

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B093

Date: 11/5/05

Operator: MAP

Page 1 of 1

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:18:00											SID2 breaks in contact
10:28:30	200	0.09	0*	1							Start Profile 1 from FL110
10:29:27	500	0.09		1							FL100
10:30:18	430	0.09		2							FL090
10:31:18	400	0.09		2							FL080
10:32:14	480	0.09		3							FL070
10:33:26	500	0.09		2							FL060
10:34:26	530	0.09		2							FL050
10:36:01	400	0.09		2							FL040
10:37:29	440	0.10		10							FL030
10:39:20	420	0.09		20							FL020
10:41:13	380	0.09		50							FL010
10:44:24	350	0.09		40							End of Profile 1 @ 50'
10:44:58											Start Run 1.1 @ 100'
10:45:00	420	0.09		20							
10:47:00											End of Run 1.1
10:47:40											Start Run 1.2 @ 100'
10:48:00	380	0.09		20							
10:49:40											End of Run 1.2
10:50:12											Start Run 1.3 @ 100'
10:51:00	350	0.09		20							
10:52:12											End of Run 1.3
10:53:07											Start Run 1.4 @ 100'
10:54:00	540	0.09		15							
10:55:10											End of Run 1.4 Start Profile 2
10:57:01											End of P 2 Start Run 2.1 @ 1000'
10:58:00	500	0.09		20							
11:00:48											End of Run 2.1
11:00:48											Start Run 3.1 @ 1000'
11:01:00	350	0.09		10							
11:02:45											End of Run 3.1
11:03:41											Start Run 3.2 @ 1000'
11:04:00	350	0.09		15							
11:05:47											End of Run 3.2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B093

Date: 11/5/05

Operator: MAP

Page 2 of 2

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:07:39											Start Run 3.3 @ 1000'
11:08:00	380	0.09	0	15							
11:09:38											End of Run 3.3
11:10:00											Start Run 4.1 @ 1000'
11:11:00	400	0.08		15							
11:12:04											End of Run 4.1 Start Run 5.1
11:13:00	320	0.08	1	10							
11:14:06											End of Run 5.1
11:14:42											Start Run 5.2 @ 1000'
11:15:00	380	0.09		10							
11:16:48											End of Run 5.2 Start Run 5.3
11:17:00	560	0.09		20							
11:18:48											End of Run 5.3
11:19:52	430	0.09		20							Start profile 3 from 1000'
11:21:50	330	0.09		20							FL020
11:22:48	330	0.09		10							FL030
11:23:47	440	0.09		2							FL040
11:24:49											End of P3 & Start R 6.1 @ FL050
11:25:00	480	0.09		2							
11:26:63											End of Run 6.1
11:27:38											Start Run 6.2 @ FL050
11:28:00	450	0.09		2							
11:29:48											End of Run 6.2
11:31:31											Start Profile 5 from FL050
11:32:15	290	0.09		2							FL060
11:33:20	320	0.09		2							FL070
11:34:10	220	0.09		2							FL080
11:35:02	230	0.09									FL090
11:35:58	400	0.09									End of Profile 5 @ FL100
11:36:17											Start Run 7.1 @ FL100
11:37:00	430	0.09		2							
11:37:20											End of Run 7.1
11:38:05											Start Run 7.2 @ FL100

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B093

Date: 11/5/05

Operator: MAP

Page 3 of 3

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:39:00	440	0.09	1	2							
11:40:01											End of Run 7.2
11:41:45											Start Run 7.3 @ FL100
11:42:00	290	0.09		2							
11:43:49											End of Run 7.3
11:45:14											Start Run 7.4 @ FL100
11:46:00	380	0.09		2							
11:46:16											End of Run 7.4
11:46:35											Start Run 7.6 @ FL100
11:47:00	400	0.09		2							
11:48:40											End of Run 7.6
11:50:41											Start Run 7.8 @ FL100
11:51:00	250	0.09									
11:52:29											End of Run 7.8
11:53:10	430	0.09		2							Start Profile 6 from FL100
11:53:49	430	0.09		2							FL110
11:55:53	240	0.09		2							FL130
11:57:59	20	0.09		2							FL150
11:59:04	20	0.09		1							FL160
12:00:54	20	0.09		1							FL180
12:01:55	20	0.09									FL190
12:02:52	20	0.09									FL200
12:03:53	15	0.09									FL210
12:05:00	10	0.09		1							FL220
12:06:08	15	0.10		5							FL230
12:07:02	30	0.10		5							FL240
12:07:57	60	0.09		3							End of Profile 6 @ FL250
12:08:55											Start Run 8.1 @ FL250
12:09:00	45	0.09		2							
12:10:57											End of Run 8.1
12:11:36											Start Run 8.2 @ FL250
12:12:00	75	0.09		2							
12:13:37											End of Run 8.2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B093

Date: 11/5/05

Operator: MAP

Page 4 of 4

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks	
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size		Habit
12:16:12									Noise			Start Run 8.3 @ FL250
12:17:00	25	0.09	1		1				Noise			Rearm 2DP to 1 12:15
12:18:12									Noise			End of Run 8.3
12:20:02									Noise			Start Run 8.4 @ FL250
12:21:00	20	0.09			1				Noise			
12:22:18									Noise			End of Run 8.4
12:23:55									Noise			Start Run 8.6 @ FL250
12:24:00	45	0.09			1				Noise			
12:26:08									Noise			End of Run 8.6
12:26:14									Noise			Start Run 8.7 @ FL250
12:27:00	30	0.09							Noise			
12:28:25									Noise			End of Run 8.7
12:28:54									Noise			Start Orbit 1 @ FL250
12:30:55									Noise			End of Orbit 1
12:31:26									Noise			Start Orbit 2 @ FL250
12:32:57									Noise			End of Orbit 2
12:33:40									Noise			Start of Orbit 3 @ FL250
12:35:07									Noise			End of Orbit 3
12:35:35									Noise			Start Run 8.8 @ FL250
12:36:00	15	0.09			1				Noise			
12:36:41									Noise			End of Run 8.8
12:38:38	20	0.09			1				Noise			Start Profile 7 from FL250
12:39:23	15	0.09			1				Noise			FL260
12:40:22	10	0.09			1				Noise			FL270
12:41:20	10	0.09			1				Noise			FL280
12:42:35	10	0.09			1				Noise			FL290
12:43:20	5	0.09							Noise			End of Profile 7 @ FL300
12:43:55									Noise			Start Run 9.1 @ FL300
12:44:00	6	0.09							Noise			
12:45:55									Noise			End of Run 9.1
12:46:37									Noise			Start Run 9.2 @ FL300
12:47:00	15	0.21			1				Noise			
12:48:37									Noise			End of Run 9.2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B093

Date: 11/5/05

Operator: MAP

Page 5 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:50:43								Noise			Start Run 9.3 @ FL300
12:51:00	10	0.09	1	1				Noise			
12:52:42								Noise			End of Run 9.3
12:55:43								Noise			Start Profile 8 from FL300
12:57:05								Noise			FL310
12:58:20	15	0.09	1					Noise			FL320
13:00:15								Noise			End P 8 & Start R 10.1 @ FL330
13:01:27								Noise			End of Run 10.1
13:05:03								Noise			Start Run 10.2 @ FL330
13:06:00	25	0.11						Noise			
13:07:08								Noise			End of Run 10.2
13:08:20								Noise			Start Run 10.3 @ FL330
13:09:00	25	0.12						Noise			
13:10:22								Noise			End of Run 10.3
13:12:19								Noise			Start Run 10.4 @ FL330
13:13:00	20	0.11						Noise			
13:14:19								Noise			End of Run 10.4
13:17:37								Noise			Start Run 10.5 @ FL330
13:18:00	15	0.09						Noise			
13:19:35								Noise			End of Run 10.5
13:20:31								Noise			Start Run 10.6 @ FL330
13:21:00	25	0.11						Noise			
13:22:28								Noise			End of Run 10.6
13:22:50	25	0.10						Noise			Start Profile 9 from FL330
13:24:15	20	0.10						Noise			FL320
13:25:13	10	0.09						Noise			FL310
13:26:03	15	0.12						Noise			FL300
13:26:52	55	0.08						Noise			FL290
13:30:25	30	0.09						Noise			FL280
13:31:22	75	0.08						Noise			FL270
13:32:27	20	0.08						Noise			FL260
13:33:38								Noise			End of P9 @ Start R11.1 @ FL250
13:34:00	35	0.09						Noise			

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B093

Date: 11/5/05

Operator: MAP

Page 6 of 6

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks	
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size		Habit
13:35:40									Noise			End of Run 11.1
13:36:13									Noise			Start Run 11.2 @ FL250
13:37:00	10	0.09	1						Noise			
13:38:30									Noise			End of Run 11.2
13:38:45									Noise			Start Run 11.3 @ FL250
13:39:00	30	0.08							Noise			
13:40:44									Noise			End of Run 11.3
13:41:01									Noise			Start Run 11.4 @ FL250
13:42:00	25	0.09							Noise			
13:43:02									Noise			End of Run 11.4
13:45:17									Noise			Start Run 11.5 @ FL250
13:46:00	20	0.09							Noise			
13:47:35									Noise			End of Run 11.5
13:48:08	20	0.09							Noise			Start Profile 10 from FL250
13:49:09	75	0.08							Noise			FL240
13:50:00	170	0.08							Noise			FL230
13:51:01	150	0.08							Noise			FL220
13:52:09	20	0.08							Noise			FL210
13:53:28	50	0.08							Noise			FL200
13:54:30	140	0.08							Noise			FL190
13:55:34	55	0.08							Noise			FL180
13:56:33	40	0.08							Noise			FL170
14:00:15	35	0.08							Noise			FL160
14:01:25	35	0.08							Noise			FL150
14:02:30	70	0.08			1				Noise			FL140
14:03:35	70	0.08			2				Noise			FL130
14:04:42	490	0.09			2				Noise			FL120
14:05:53	540	0.09			2							FL110
14:07:02	530	0.09			2							End of P10 Start Run 12.1 FL100
14:08:00	540	0.09			2							
14:09:00												End of Run 12.1
14:09:40												Start Run 12.2 @ FL100
14:10:00	535	0.08			2							

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B093**

Date: 11/05/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	Y
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CPI	N	
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS		N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	Y	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS		N
PERCA	Y	N	Bag Sampling		N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B093

Date: 11/05/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off .
2. Core CNC – continuing problem with data recording/transfer. Instrument appears to be working.
3. Smell of Butanol possibly following a pitch oscillation run. Likely source is CNC or possibly AMS instrument?

Aircraft

Flight B093 10:17:01

Heading 57 deg Speed 237 knots Height 11.0kft Press 669mb

Lat 52.6N Long 0.4E Wind 4 ms-1/ 16 deg

Temp -12.1C Dewpoint -23.26C

From 09:33:30 to now

Didn't capture zoom picture

	Current values		
---	STATIC PRESSURE	669.55	mb
+++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-12.1	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-23.26	deg C

Ascent from t/o

Flight B093 10:46:41

Heading 353 deg Speed 194 knots Height -0.2kft Press 1022mb

Lat 53.8N Long 1.8E Wind 5 ms-1/ 353 deg

Temp 7.65C Dewpoint 3.23C

From 09:33:30 to now

	Current values		
---	STATIC PRESSURE	1022.89	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	7.65	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	3.24	deg C

Ascent from t/o
+ descent over sea (overload)

New plot, same times

Flight B093 11:20:01

Heading 290 deg Speed 194 knots Height 0.8kft Press 983mb
 Lat 54.2N Long 1.8E Wind 4 ms-1/ 353 deg
 Temp 4.38C Dewpoint 1.2C
 From 10:32:18 to now

Current values				
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	40800	secs	☉ All
—	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	4.38	deg C	☉
—	NONDEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	4.58	deg C	☉
—	TURB PROBE ATTACK DIFF	-0.31	mb	☉
—	TURB PROBE SIDESLIP DIFF	-0.02	mb	☉

New plot, same times

Flight B093 11:35:48

Heading 45 deg Speed 232 knots Height 9.9kft Press 698mb

Lat 54.2N Long 1.1E Wind 7 ms-1/ 351 deg

Temp -11.42C Dewpoint -23.48C

From 11:00:01 to now

Current values			
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	41748	secs
—	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-11.42	deg C
—	NONDEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-11.33	deg C

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These images come from satellites which remain above a fixed point on the Earth (i.e. they are "geostationary"). The infrared image shows the invisible infrared radiation emitted directly by cloud tops and land or ocean surfaces. The warmer an object is, the more intensely it emits radiation, thus allowing us to determine its temperature. These intensities can be converted into greyscale tones, with cooler temperatures showing as lighter tones and warmer as darker.

Lighter areas of cloud show where the cloud tops are cooler and therefore where weather features like fronts and shower clouds are. The advantage of infrared images is that they can be recorded 24 hours a day. However, low cloud, having similar temperatures to the underlying surface, are less easily discernable. Coast-lines and lines of

Dave K 01392 884285

Flight B093

cloud after t/o

cloud on transit after t/o

over sea, faint wing tip vapour trail

towards coast, more Cu over land

coast, Cu over land

another view over to coast

zoom in to coast detail

[<--Previous](#) [Up](#) [Next-->](#)

cloud after t/o

HORACE time = 10:05:13 View to port from aft core console

[<--Previous](#) [Up](#) [Next-->](#)

zoom in to coast detail

HORACE time = 13:14:37 View to aft/port from aft core console

another view over to coast

[<--Previous](#) [Up](#) [Next-->](#)

another view over to coast

HORACE time = 13:14:37 View to aft/port from aft core console

[<--Previous](#) [Up](#) [Next-->](#)

coast, Cu over land

HORACE time = 12:48:09 View to port from aft core console

towards coast, more Cu over land

[<--Previous](#) [Up](#) [Next-->](#)

towards coast, more Cu over land

HORACE time = 12:15:52 View to port from aft core console

over sea, faint wing tip vapour trail

[<--Previous](#) [Up](#) [Next-->](#)

over sea, faint wing tip vapour trail

HORACE time = 11:07:09 View to port from aft core console

[<--Previous](#) [Up](#) [Next-->](#)

cloud on transit after t/o

HORACE time = 10:06:21 View to port from aft core console